

RISK FACTORS OF MYOCARDIAL ELECTRICAL INSTABILITY IN PATIENTS AFTER ACUTE MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION AND THEIR DYNAMICS FOLLOWING SURGICAL REVASCULARIZATION.

Rasulov A.Sh.

Mullabaeva G.U.

Pulatov Kh.I.

**Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical
Medical Center of Cardiology
Tashkent, Uzbekistan**

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ABSTRACT

Cardiovascular diseases remain the leading cause of mortality worldwide, with a significant proportion of deaths related to sudden cardiac death (SCD). Patients who have experienced acute myocardial infarction (AMI) are at particularly high risk, especially within the first year. Myocardial electrical instability, reflected by ventricular arrhythmias, heart rate variability (HRV), and QT interval parameters, plays a crucial role in predicting adverse outcomes.

Background:

Cardiovascular diseases remain the leading cause of mortality worldwide, with a significant proportion of deaths related to sudden cardiac death (SCD). Patients who have experienced acute myocardial infarction (AMI) are at particularly high risk, especially within the first year. Myocardial electrical instability, reflected by ventricular arrhythmias, heart rate variability (HRV), and QT interval parameters, plays a crucial role in predicting adverse outcomes.

Objective:

To assess the risk factors of myocardial electrical instability in post-AMI patients and evaluate their changes after surgical myocardial revascularization.

Methods:

The study included 170 patients aged 40–76 years (mean age 59.7±8.1 years) with a history of AMI who were admitted for coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG). All patients underwent clinical, biochemical, echocardiographic, coronary angiographic, and 24-hour Holter ECG monitoring.

HRV parameters (SDNN, SDANN, rMSSD, pNN50), spectral indices, QT interval, corrected QT (QTc), and QT dispersion (QTd) were analyzed. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results:

The majority of patients were male (88.2%) with predominantly first-time AMI (85.3%). Overweight and obesity were common.

No significant changes were observed in SDNN values over one year (40.9 ± 13.7 ms vs. 40.6 ± 12.6 ms; $p=0.126$). However, a significant decrease in HRV triangular index (HRV TI) was noted (9.2 ± 2.6 vs. 8.6 ± 2 ; $p=0.002$).

A statistically significant reduction in QT interval duration was observed after revascularization (403.1 ± 39.2 ms vs. 379 ± 26.8 ms; $p=0.002$), suggesting improvement in myocardial repolarization. No significant changes were found in QTc or QT dispersion.

Conclusion:

Surgical myocardial revascularization is associated with improvement in myocardial electrical stability, particularly reflected by shortening of the QT interval. HRV parameters remain important predictors of sudden cardiac death in post-AMI patients. Further studies are required to clarify the prognostic role of electrical instability markers following different revascularization strategies.

